

**INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AT PRE-SCHOOL AND
IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**

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Abstract:

In this article, we illuminate modern ways of educating children in their early ages by using various techniques in order to interact them in a field of learning foreign languages by collecting different data from relevant researches. Because it is so important to find appropriate strategies while conducting lessons and teaching effectively. And significance acquiring knowledge of language for every person is huge, knowing language is a lot more than knowing a couple of words out of the dictionary, it is a lot more than being able to ask where the bathroom is or telling the time of the day.

Key words: innovative methods, teaching, preschool, learning language, games, improves memory

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Parents involve their children to pre-school education in variety fields, especially to learn new language whereas teaching youngsters to something is mostly annoying even in their native language. That's why attracting them to the lesson demand patience and creativity. However extensive investigations show that nowadays there are so many methods such as visual, listening, playing interactive games and etc. to educate them curiously and working with such kind of modern, advanced technologies and finding suitable one, improve effectiveness in language learning. But some people consider learning ability and being multilingual is gifted so all people who want to learn cannot do. Polyglot Tim Doner said, there is no prodigy person, there are just dedicated people. Find your way, work and do. And there is may be question, why learning new language is important? "Learning language helps to improve critical thinking and problem-solving skills and in fact, language learners tend to have bigger brain with better skills than ordinary people. Furthermore, there is a real tie between language and culture, there are so much language can tell you about one culture's mindset-Tim said.

The use of games in teaching helps to maintain interest in the English language, and also makes it easier to assimilate, consolidate and master the lesson material. With the help of game, you can achieve unprecedented success in teaching children. The most elementary education, that is, preschool teaching of languages and other subjects, of course, should begin with game methods. The advantages of this method are that it helps to form a strong attachment

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between the teacher and the child, and also the stimulation of the senses helps the child to know his personality and grow up to be comprehensively developed, and also this method of extraordinary education brings up original-minded children.[1]

Rolling dice.

Here again, you can turn on your imagination. When I started teaching in my school, I just used a square box and later the school bought a big one on Taobao (was rather cheap). On each side, I stuck pictures of words we have learned with kids. This game is suitable for all topics you can think about. For beginners, it can be numbers, colors, body parts, animals and so on with a question What is this? What do you see. For a higher level, kids prepare more questions, for example for body parts you can ask What are these? They are fingers? "How many fingers do you have? "I have 10 fingers? for fruits, it can be What is this?" It is a lemon. "Is it sweet? "No, it is sour.

Maze game

For the summary lessons, we use dice to play a maze game. This needs a bit more preparation and time to play, but it is great for reviewing. You place flashcards one after another on the floor all over the room. You also can add question cards and bombs (cards with additional exercises like stand on one leg or jump to the next card. Kids take turns to roll a die, call the number and move to the next spot to name the flashcard or answer the question.[2]

Teaching through multimedia devices is also common way of teaching children so both teachers and parents use televisions and mobile phones in various purposes such as learning something or just to interact when they are busy and it really works. Watching cartoons and movies is enjoyed by children as well improving their language. "It is really helpful in any kind of language learning because it exposes you to the normal rate of speech and language and maybe more colloquial register than you get in the text book. I think it trains you also to be able to comprehend a lot more " said Tim.

Teaching with interesting things can help teachers to attract student's attention because children are playful therefore, they tend to turn aside during lesson. Training by colorful pictures and connecting all related topics help learn new information by heart since there both visual memory and echoic memory work

Reward their accomplishments

Celebration and rewarding are the best way to encourage students to develop and to be better as well supporting their achievements, often preparing special room to celebrate refresh them to learn. Furthermore, when you celebrate accomplishments, you help students see that they're making progress and moving along the road to fluency. And when you point out their successes, they'll be more motivated to reach for the next goal.

Skype for Real Conversations

Skype real conversation is the program can give real English conversation practice with native speakers without buying ticket. You can ask some of your friends from the ESL world (or even other English-speaking friends and family) to donate an hour or two for Skype conversations with your classroom.[3]

There are also so many simple but interesting ways can be used as additional task during the lesson according to children's interests such as singing songs, dancing, drawing. Using variety of methods and changing them step by step to new one grab students' attention and they will not get bored in lesson.

International Conference

HUMANISTIC ROLE OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE CONTEMPORARY GLOBALIZATION

Learning new languages give opportunity to contact with new people and getting new information about their culture, It broadens also students' mind by knowing their education, art and such kind of limitless fields. And the most notable thing "If you talk to a man in a language he understands, that goes to his head. If you talk to him in his language, that goes to his heart." Nelson Mandella said. It is obviously true maybe we can speak fluently in different languages but unfortunately, we cannot feel this language at all.

The study of foreign languages and cultures leads students to become more responsible and committed global citizens. It reduces the barriers to travel and, therefore, encourages continued exposure to other cultures and allows individuals to interact more fully with others [4]. Much has been written about how many jobs in the future will be automated – with tasks requiring ingenuity and creativity being left to humans. How then to build creative thinking skills in children? One of the surprising ways is by learning a second language. Several studies have demonstrated greater creativity and problem-solving skills amongst bilinguals.

Learning a foreign language helps children see the world through different lenses. The ability to consider multiple viewpoints to a problem is a cornerstone of creative problem solving.

Language education is critical for the workforce of the future and being bilingual can broaden career options. Many jobs in education, healthcare, social work, national security, translation, tourism, and international business require or favor candidates who are bilingual, resulting in more job opportunities for those who can speak a second language. And speaking a foreign language can make it easier to be eligible for jobs, internships and work-study programs in other countries – especially if you have critical skills.

It improves your memory. The more you use your brain to learn new skills, the more your brain's functions work. Learning a new language pushes your brain to get familiar with new grammar and vocabulary rules. It allows you to train your memory to remember new words, make connections between them, and use them in contextual situations. [5]

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